

Erotylid sp. nov. MS 6
Cycad fungus beetle

Decoding
South Africa's
Biodiversity

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Group: Insect

Size: 3.5-5 mm length

Distribution:

Eastern Cape in the vicinity of Kariega and Gqeberha.

Importance:

This cycad fungus beetle is a pollinator of highly endangered cycad species. Genome sequencing will assist in accurate species identification and classification, as well as in determining host specificity, thereby informing targeted conservation and recovery plans.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 40.47 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 4.63 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm

Genome Length: 0.89 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 99.6% [Single: 97.3%, Duplicated: 2.3%]

BUSCO database: insecta

Assembly N50: 2 317.9 kilobases

Contig number: 5 131

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